

INVESTIGATION, PROTOTYPING AND DEPLOYMENT OF A HIGHER-LEVEL SERVICE FOR DATA TRANSPORT

*WORK PACKAGE 4: BIG-DATA ELECTRON AND
CORRELATIVE MICROSCOPY FROM
INSTRUMENT TO PUBLICATION*

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JULY 2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5124450

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This project is supported by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) and the following partners. The ARDC is enabled by NCRIS.

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Executive summary

Moving data reliably, securely and at high speed was identified as important in the report “Orchestration and management of data generated by big-data electron microscopy instruments: A Discovery report”. The present report focuses on the selection of an appropriate tool for data transport, namely Globus, and its prototyping, testing and deployment at two sites. User documentation and guidelines to deploy Globus have been developed and made available online in open access. This work was undertaken under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication” of the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project.

1. Introduction

Traditional data movement protocols and tools such as SFTP, SCP and rsync are widely used but have limitations when it comes to achieving high-speed data throughput on fast networks (10 Gb/s and above). These tools can also show reduced efficiency in cases of high network latency. Network latency is the delay in transferring data over a network from a point of transmission of the data to a point of reception of those data. Several factors contribute to network latency, including the distance between the data transmission and reception points (that is the longer the distance, the higher the latency), and the nature and configuration (such as security measures) of the network components involved in data communication, both software and infrastructure.

To overcome such limitations and to provide a more common data-transport platform across operating systems, higher-level transport tools are required. Globus¹ was identified as an effective, higher-level data transport tool to investigate in the review “Orchestration and management of data generated by big-data electron microscopy instruments: A Discovery report”.^[1] Indeed, Globus presents several main advantages: it is readily available, free (that is no licensing cost) and can be integrated into customised data workflows using its API (Application Programming Interface). The online documentation is comprehensive and provides a range of examples of Globus integration.^{2,3} Note, Globus also offers a subscription service that provides additional support and functionality, including “managed” endpoints that allow greater data-transfer rates, the ability to share data with other Globus users and monthly reports of data transfers. In addition, Globus has been widely adopted among academic institutions globally. Thus, the session at the 2019 eResearch Australasia conference dedicated to Globus sparked significant interest from the represented institutions.

The focus on Globus in this work is consistent with the current Australian national context. AARNet (Australia’s Academic and Research Network) is negotiating a subscription with the Globus development team in the United States that would cover interested Australian research institutions. As part of the trial phase led by AARNet, the institutions involved in this work, specifically Monash University (via the Monash eResearch Centre), the University of Wollongong, The University of Queensland and The University of Western Australia have been granted access to features in Globus that are normally available through a paid subscription. In the work presented here, prototyping, testing and deployment of Globus were carried out by Monash University and the University of Wollongong in collaboration with AARNet.

A notable alternative to Globus is the product Aspera provided by IBM.⁴ Aspera can be used to transfer data at high speed over networks. In many ways, it is a competitor product to Globus. In fact, Aspera was mentioned alongside Globus in “Orchestration and management of data generated by big-data electron microscopy instruments: A Discovery report”.^[1] However, unlike Globus, Aspera requires the purchase of a licence. The Australian National Data Service (ANDS) that preceded the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) funded

¹ <https://www.globus.org>

² <https://docs.globus.org>

³ <https://globus-integration-examples.readthedocs.io>

⁴ <https://www.ibm.com/au-en/products/aspera>

the program “Research Data Storage (RDS)” that purchased several perpetual licenses for Aspera nodes. The Monash eResearch Centre currently holds a license that was inherited from The University of Melbourne subsequent to the decommissioning of its Aspera node. As a result, Monash University can use Aspera as an additional high-level data-transfer service for its high-performance computing facility MASSIVE. However, given that the deployment of Aspera across several institutions in Australia would imply the purchase of several licences, Globus remained the preferred choice for the present project.

In this report, the higher-level transport service Globus is briefly described. Then, the prototyping, testing and deployment of Globus at two locations (Monash University and the University of Wollongong) are presented. Links to documentation to assist with deployment and use of Globus are provided.

This work was undertaken under the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project, in particular under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication”. This report is intended as the conclusion of the work planned for deliverable WP4.1: “Investigate, prototype and deploy a higher-level service for data transport”.

2. Description of Globus

Globus is a not-for-profit service for data transport developed and operated by the University of Chicago.[2,3] It is primarily driven for researchers and research organisations.

The schematic in Figure 1 shows that Globus can be used to transport data between a range of storage devices and systems, that is personal computers, data stores, compute servers such as high-performance computing facilities, and cloud stores including commercial solutions such as DropBox, Amazon Web Services S3, Microsoft OneDrive, Microsoft Azure, IBM Cloud, Google Cloud and Google Drive. Globus can also be used to get data off instruments directly.

Figure 1 Schematic overview of data transport using Globus between systems and devices where data are stored, processed, visualised or generated.

In the terminology used in Globus, the transfer locations (both source and destination) are named “endpoints”. When a resource (for example a server, storage system, instrument or personal computer) is defined as an endpoint, it becomes available to authorised users who can transfer files to or from this endpoint.⁵ When an endpoint is part of a paid subscription, it is referred to as a “managed endpoint” and has full administrative capabilities enabled (that is features such as data sharing and usage reporting).⁶

Globus Connect is the component of the Globus service that needs to be installed locally on a system or device in order to create an endpoint. There are two versions of Globus Connect: Globus Connect Personal to create an endpoint on a single-user system (personal workstation, desktop and laptop), and Globus Connect Server for multi-user, Linux computing and storage resources. Endpoints are thus often called “personal endpoints” or “server endpoints” when they refer to Globus Connect Personal or Globus Connect Server, respectively. Using Globus is possible via a web-based graphical user interface (GUI), a command-line interface (CLI) and via an API integrated into applications. CLI and API allow for automation of the data transfer.

Key aspects in how Globus works is that it provides fast, reliable and secure transfer of data between two endpoints, regardless of whether the data consist of a few or many small or large folders or files. The high transfer rate is obtained by the use of multiple network sockets simultaneously to transfer data. The reliability of the service is ensured by the fact that Globus is more robust than tools such as rsync and SFTP with respect to network fluctuations. It can restart a transfer automatically in case of failure because of network glitches or high network latency amongst other causes that can lead to an unexpected termination of a data transfer. Finally, the security of the service rests upon a range of factors, including the use of existing identities provided and managed by institutions to use Globus, integrity check of transferred data and the encryption of the metadata associated with the transferred data and created by Globus for data control (for example to ensure that filenames and path names are conserved).

3. Prototyping of Globus

Prototyping is the process of installing and configuring software for evaluation in a small-scale and safe environment.

The prototyping of Globus was carried out at Monash University (MASSIVE) and the University of Wollongong. At MASSIVE, NECTAR⁷ virtual machines were used to test installs of Globus Connect Server. The use of NECTAR virtual machines was preferred because those machines sat outside the MASSIVE network so the initial installation, configuration and various trials and errors to understand how to deploy Globus at a larger scale on a server like MASSIVE posed no risk to the research data stored on MASSIVE.

Initial work focused on authentication and authorisation. Authentication is the process of validating who a user claims to be. Authorisation is determining what resources an authenticated user has access to. The web-based Globus portal⁸ provides several options for

⁵ <https://docs.globus.org/faq/globus-connect-endpoints>

⁶ <https://www.globus.org/subscriptions>

⁷ <https://nectar.org.au>

⁸ <https://app.globus.org>

authentication: using a Google account, an ORCID identifier, a local Globus identifier, or using login details for organisations listed in a drop-down list under “Look-up your organization” in the Globus web interface. Those organisations (from here on referred to as “listed organisations”) correspond to organisations that participate in eduGAIN.⁹ eduGAIN is a global service that interconnects identity federations around the world, thereby allowing users from participating organisations to access services developed by other participating federations using single sign-on (SSO). In Australia, the participation in eduGAIN is via the Australian Access Federation.

When work in Work Package 4 commenced, Monash University was not a member of eduGAIN so users at Monash University were required to login to Globus via the Google authentication option. As the latest version of Globus Connect Server (version 5) supported—and still supports—only listed organisations, the work on prototyping Globus at Monash University focused on version 4 of Globus Connect Server that was open to non-listed organisations. Globus Connect Server v4 allows different mechanisms to authenticate and authorise users to endpoints. At MASSIVE, running MyProxy OAuth was chosen. MyProxy OAuth is a service that allows users to delegate their MASSIVE credentials to Globus Online. Two main configurations were tested at MASSIVE. The first was running Globus Connect Server on a single machine that provided the authentication and also acted as the endpoint to handle data transfers. The second configuration was to run two machines where the authentication was on one machine and the endpoint for data transfers was on the other.

Prototyping of Globus at the University of Wollongong happened in two stages: first, Globus was installed on a desktop using Globus Connect Personal, then Globus was installed on a server using Globus Connect Server. Unlike Monash University, the University of Wollongong was a listed organisation when Work Package 4 started so Globus Connect Server version 5 (5.4) was installed.

4. Testing of Globus

As the prototyping and testing of Globus were integrated into the trial phase of Globus led by AARNet, Monash University and the University of Wollongong were able to use features in Globus normally accessible through the paid subscription only. As a result, the endpoints used for testing are referred to as managed endpoints. Endpoints were instantiated using Globus Connect Server unless otherwise specified. Note, after successful prototyping of Globus at Monash University using the NECTAR nodes, Globus Connect Server was installed on MASSIVE for testing.

One of the features available to managed endpoints is how the network capability is used to ensure maximum transfer speed. The network use can be set to four preset configurations in Globus: “normal”, “aggressive”, “minimal” and “custom”. The main difference between the normal and aggressive modes is in the number of concurrent network sockets that can be recruited, the aggressive mode leading to the maximum transfer speed possible at a given time. Note, as a result of the aggressive mode, the network at an institution may be impacted adversely when shared with other users. The choice of using the normal or aggressive mode

⁹ <https://edugain.org>

Figure 2 Schematic of the transfer routes investigated for testing the data transfer rates obtained using Globus.

is therefore a balance between network usage and speed based on a given circumstance at an institution. Depending on the local usage and capability at an institution, the aggressive mode can be the default configuration.

Data-transfer speeds were investigated using the dataset `500GB-in-large-files` located at the Globus endpoint managed by AARNet on a server in Melbourne and called `AARNet-Public-Test-Share`. Figure 2 displays the transfer routes that were examined to measure rates of data transfer (that is transfer speed) obtained when moving data from the AARNet server to MASSIVE or the University of Wollongong, and between MASSIVE and the University of Wollongong. The Globus endpoint at the University of Wollongong was located at the Cryogenic Electron Microscopy facility.

Table 1 shows a summary of recent rates of data transfer obtained. Note, it is not possible to provide an exact, one-to-one comparison of transfer rates between instances when Globus was used and instances when alternative, well-established tools such as SFTP or rsync were used because the hardware, the software and the modality (web GUI versus command-line interface) associated with each method were different. For example, a Globus endpoint cannot transfer data using rsync. Nonetheless, as a reference, from experience over the past years, data transfer without Globus between MASSIVE and the Cryogenic Electron Microscopy facility at the University of Wollongong has operated at a rate of about 200 MB/s in general in both directions. As can be seen in Table 1, data transfer tests using the dataset `500GB-in-large-files` between the `AARNet-Public-Test-Share` endpoint and the MASSIVE endpoint achieved a rate of 1.07 GB/s, that is 500 GB transferred in under 8 min (7 min 44 s). Notably, test transfers between the University of Wollongong using the same data set showed a dramatic increase in speed by nearly 80–90 % between the normal and aggressive modes for network use, in both directions (370 and 660 MB/s in the normal and aggressive modes, respectively, from the University of Wollongong to MASSIVE; and 240 and 460 MB/s in the normal and aggressive modes, respectively, from MASSIVE to the University of Wollongong).

Furthermore, testing at the University of Wollongong illustrated how network configurations and hardware could affect transfer rates. Initial testing at the University of Wollongong was performed using a Globus Connect Personal endpoint. This was set up on a spare desktop computer while planning for an installation of Globus Connect Server at the university. Data transfer tests were carried out using the dataset `500GB-in-large-files`. The initial download from AARNet was transferred at 108 MB/s, taking 1 hr 17 min overall. The transfer rate was limited by the on-board 1 Gb/s network card in the computer. After the card was changed to a 10 Gb/s card, the transfer rate jumped to 370 MB/s when transferring the dataset

Table 1 Summary of the rates of data transfer obtained between Globus endpoints located in the AARNet server in Melbourne, MASSIVE and the University of Wollongong.

Transfer route ^a	Data-transfer rates	
	Using the normal mode for network use	Using the aggressive mode for network use
AARNet → MASSIVE		1.07 GB/s
AARNet → University of Wollongong*	108 MB/s	
University of Wollongong → AARNet		880 MB/s
University of Wollongong* → MASSIVE	370 MB/s	
University of Wollongong → MASSIVE	570 MB/s	660 MB/s
MASSIVE → University of Wollongong	240 MB/s	460 MB/s

^a All data transfers to or from the University of Wollongong (Cryogenic Electron Microscopy facility) were performed using a server except in the cases indicated with an asterisk when a desktop computer was used.

to the endpoint at MASSIVE, this time being limited by the speed at which the hard-disk drive could be read in the computer. Network testing and optimisation of the settings with assistance from AARNet showed that the 10 Gb/s network card could manage a sustained transfer rate of 9.3 Gb/s (1.16 GB/s) to the AARNet server in Melbourne. Therefore, this demonstrated that, at the time, if a Globus endpoint had been created on more capable hardware at the University of Wollongong, similar speeds to those achieved by MASSIVE could have been obtained.

5. Deployment of Globus

5.1. At Monash University (MASSIVE)

The deployment of Globus Connect Server v4 within MASSIVE was supported by the development of an Ansible role. Ansible is a software widely used to manage the deployment of infrastructure at MASSIVE.

Two endpoints were deployed at MASSIVE. The main endpoint, `massive#massive`, handles the authentication via the MyProxy OAuth configuration and performs data transfers. This endpoint is currently running on a development machine with 6 cores and 60 GB RAM. The second endpoint, `massive#mern`, is for big-data instruments connected to the Monash eResearch Network (MeRN). This is a private, internal 10 Gb/s network. To access `massive#mern`, the authentication is handled by the same MyProxy OAuth server installed for `massive#massive` but only data transfers from machines on the Monash eResearch Network are possible. The Ansible role was altered to cater for both endpoint installations. A public copy of the Ansible scripts and programs developed for the deployment of Globus at MASSIVE

(`massive#massive` and `massive#mern`) is available on GitHub,¹⁰ alongside end-user documentation.¹¹

5.2. At the University of Wollongong

As the University of Wollongong was a listed organisation, Globus Connect Server v5.4 was installed on a local server at the Cryogenic Electron Microscopy facility. Changes in the firewall settings of the university to allow Globus traffic to the file server were required. Given this would be exposing research data to the outside world, the Cyber Security Team within the university's central IT unit expressed reservations initially regarding the deployment and use of Globus. However, that Globus was a member of EDUCAUSE¹² demonstrated that Globus was a trusted service amongst research and academic institutions. EDUCAUSE is an association in the United States of higher-education institutions, corporations serving higher-education information technology and other related organisations that aims to lead, manage, and use information technology to advance higher education. Indeed, Globus is used by a larger number of universities and leading public and private organisations in the United States. As a result, changes to the university's firewall settings were authorised and Globus Connect Server v5.4 was installed. Note, the changes in the firewall rule implemented by the Cyber Security Team were different from the firewall setup recommended in the Globus documentation. This may be of interest to organisations wishing to deploy Globus. Further details are available upon request.

6. Outcome

The Globus-based data-transport service at Monash University (MASSIVE) and the University of Wollongong has been operational since March 2021. Although the current number of users can be regarded as low, it has been increasing steadily since March 2021. As the Globus service is being promoted, the number of users and data volumes transferred are expected to increase. Notably, in February 2021, 6 and 8 TB of data were transferred from Tokyo University in Japan and University of California, Berkeley in the United States to MASSIVE, respectively.

Future plans at MASSIVE include the addition of new nodes dedicated to data transfer and the installation of the endpoint `massive#massive` across two machines to load balance as opposed to one currently. A larger server for `massive#mern` has been requested to take better advantage of the 10 Gb/s network for faster throughput. The user documentation for Globus at MASSIVE¹¹ will be further expanded to include the Globus command-line interface (Globus CLI) and how this can assist users. Monash University has recently become a member of eduGAIN so Globus can now be upgraded to Globus Connect Server v5.4 on MASSIVE. To assist the community, the Ansible scripts have been revisited and altered to support version v5.4. They have been made available on GitHub.¹³ These scripts will be used to replace the current Globus v4 with v5.4 at the next MASSIVE maintenance period.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/Globus-Endpoint-deployment/tree/globusv4>

¹¹ <https://docs.massive.org.au/M3/transferring-files.html#globus>

¹² <https://www.educause.edu>

¹³ <https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/Globus-Endpoint-deployment>

A Globus endpoint has been installed at the University of Wollongong to assist users in moving cryo-electron microscopy datasets into MASSIVE. It is expected that the planned upgrade of Globus Connect Server to version 5.4 at MASSIVE along with the new data-transfer nodes will further increase the transfer speeds from the University of Wollongong to MASSIVE.

7. Conclusion

The prototyping, testing and deployment of Globus at two institutions, Monash University and the University of Wollongong, has shown that Globus is an efficient, reliable and fast service to transfer data, in particular large data volumes. Promoting Globus to facilities and researchers will be continued. The Monash eResearch Centre may expand the usage of Globus to other systems within the university in order to provide access to a wider range of storage systems offered to researchers.

8. Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Chris Myers at AARNet for his helpful advice and technical assistance during the installation and configuration of the network settings of the Globus endpoints at Monash University and the University of Wollongong.

9. Contributorship

JvS and JS designed the work, prototyped, tested and deployed Globus at their respective institution and drafted the report. DP oversaw overall progress of the work and wrote the final report.

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